

AN IOT BASED SUSTAINABLE ENERGY EFFICIENT AUTOMATED LIGHTING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for energy conservation in public spaces has driven the adoption of smart and automated lighting systems to minimize electricity wastage in a sustainable way. This study suggests an Internet of Things (IoT) based automated lighting system for both common areas and personal rooms of buildings that uses Arduino microcontrollers, light-dependent resistors (LDR) and ultrasonic sensors to increase energy efficiency. The system utilizes LDR sensors to monitor ambient light intensity, ensuring that lights are automatically turned ON or OFF based on natural daylight availability, minimizing energy consumption during daytime. Ultrasonic sensors use motion and human presence detection to turn on lights only when someone is there which further cuts down on wasteful power use. Real-time input from various sensors is processed by Arduino microcontroller integration, resulting in smooth automation that eliminates the need for manual control. This system is designed to function efficiently in large common spaces, ensuring optimal energy usage by switching off lights in unoccupied zones. The study also emphasizes how IoT-based monitoring and sensor-based automation can significantly contribute to sustainability by reducing overall power consumption and promoting responsible energy usage. Generally research is done particularly either on public spaces using LDR sensors or private spaces using arduino however however in this research both the systems are taken as a whole set and integrated to optimise energy which will overcome the inherent drawback of the existing system.

Keywords: *IoT, Arduino, LDR, Ultrasonic Sensor, Smart Lighting, Energy Efficiency, Sustainability*

1. INTRODUCTION

High automated lighting system but lack accuracy with data, time delay in detection by the sensors. The energy optimization issue is not quite addressed in those works. The aim of this research is to develop a sustainable energy-efficient IoT-based automated lighting system, countering the different issues faced in the previously mentioned systems. There are two primary methods which are implemented in this research to sensor light through Light Dependent Resistors (LDR) and motion-sensing through ultrasonic sensors. The light levels are detected and automatically works according to natural light availability. The ultrasonic sensor detects human presence or motion and keeps the lights on only if the space is occupied. Combined, these systems offer an efficient and automated approach to reducing power consumption in common public spaces while ensuring convenience for residents.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent times, the demand for cost-effective and sustainable management of resources has been increasing, drawing significant attention. Numerous studies have already been conducted to automate the lighting systems and save energy. In order to understand the current available solutions and identify their research gaps that our study intends to fill, this section goes through pertinent literature.

The study conducted by Ahmmed et al. [4] (2018) focused on automatic street light control using LDR and motion sensors. Their model was quite energy efficient since it ensured the lights function only when required. Although an effective way of energy optimization, no insights were given on energy minimization in indoor spaces.

Dutta et al. [2] (2020) introduced an Arduino-based design. They used LDR, PIR, and DHT11 sensors for automatic control of electric appliances. Their study ensured minimal power consumption in indoor settings. Their design was focused on reducing domestic energy costs, but it lacked a comprehensive framework for shared living spaces like buildings

in [8], Gaikwad et al. (2023) used IoT, LDR, and IR (Infrared) sensors as a clever method to maximize the efficiency of urban street lights, focusing on lowering the energy usage significantly by automatically adjusting street lights according to human presence and ambient lighting levels using an Arduino-based system. They successfully demonstrated the reduced electricity consumption and enhanced public safety but lacked insight on its implementation in indoor settings.

In [1], Pandey and Sagri (2020) proposed using IoT-based LDR and PIR (Passive Infrared) sensors in street lighting to help detect motion and adjust the intensity of light accordingly. Just like [3], their research showed substantial energy savings but did not focus on optimizing energy consumption in indoor environments like buildings .

Carol and Raju (2024) [5] suggested an energy-efficient lighting system. They used LDR, PIR sensors, and Arduino to automate lighting control in workplaces, demonstrating the effectiveness of automation solutions with readily available components, but overlooked the potential of ultrasonic sensors for more accurate motion detection.

Htwe et al. (2020) [7] proposed a power-saving system using LDR and PIR sensors to automate lighting control based on human presence and ambient light intensity. Just like [5], it lacks the integration of ultrasonic sensors, which could enhance motion detection accuracy.

Siti Aisyah Mohd et al.(2023) [6] proposed a system which focuses on integrating each sensor,energy measuring device and Iot system into a complete component,using wireless sensor network concept. The project shows noticeable errors with low data, accuracy is only shown when higher samples are taken which minimizes the efficiency to a certain level.

As the existing literature suggests, the LDR and motion sensors effectively reduce energy waste in various fields, such as outdoor and domestic sectors. However, there is limited research on their application in shared living spaces like buildings , where occupancy varies throughout the day.

The rigorous literature review exposes the following research questions:

- a. Whether the existing system immediately responds ?
- b. Is there any technology available to identify living beings for optimizing energy ?

The following section 3 explains the Research Design & methodology; Methods & materials and Discussion have been highlighted in section 4 & 5 respectively.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN & METHODOLOGY

The following methods shown in Figure-1 have been adopted in our work-

Figure 1. Flow chart on research methodology

The flowchart (Figure 1) shows a process for reducing energy consumption in buildings using automated sensor-based systems. It begins with a Literature Review, followed by a decision point to determine if the solution is possible. After that it suggests three major approaches : LDR System , Integrated System or Ultrasonic Sensor. In the LDR approach, the system checks luminance; if luminance is low, the LED glows; otherwise it does not. In the Ultrasonic Sensor approach, the system detects if a person is inside, if yes, the LED glows; otherwise, it does not. All pathways

ultimately lead to the Stop node, concluding the process. In the Integrated System, an LDR sensor ensures the LED remains off during the day, while at night, an ultrasonic sensor detects motion, if motion is detected, the LED glows; otherwise, it does not.

4. Materials and Methods

Materials Used

The following equipments are used in our approach for optimizing energy :

- A) **LDR (LIGHT DEPENDENT RESISTOR)** : It works on the principle of photoconductivity. When light falls on the material the resistance of the material decreases. It is made from cadmium sulphide. The Arduino detects the changes and provides output such that the led is high when the natural light is sufficient and low when it is dark outside. Photons from intense light excite the semiconductor material's electrons, making them more conductive and lowering resistance. On the other hand, less electrons are excited in dark environments, which lowers conductivity and raises resistance. Because of this feature, LDRs can be utilized in automatic lighting systems, which use ambient light levels to operate LEDs, streetlights, and security systems, among other devices.
- B) **LED (LIGHT EMITTING DIODE)** : An Light Emitting Diode(LED) that emits light when electric current passes through it in forward direction. To produce energy in the form of photons (light), electrons from the N-type region recombine with holes in the P-type region at a P-N junction. The semiconductor material's band gap energy determines the color of the light that is released; different materials produce different wavelengths. LEDs use less energy and produce less heat than incandescent and fluorescent bulbs, making them incredibly durable, eco-friendly, and energy-efficient. They also last for more than 50,000 hours and offer immediate illumination without the need for a warm-up period
- C) **Ultrasonic Sensor** : Ultrasonic Sensors use high-frequency sound waves to measure distance. It has a toggle that triggers a signal and an echo which receives that signal after it has reflected back from an object. The sensor uses the speed of sound to calculate distance by measuring the time it takes for the echo to return. When it comes to smart lighting systems it is perfect for because it can operate in fog and darkness. Ultrasonic sensors, as opposed to motion sensors, can identify a person's presence even while they are motionless, guaranteeing that lights will remain on when necessary. They are useful in robotics, energy-efficient lighting, and security applications because of their accuracy and dependability.

Using these materials the following methods are applied:

A) *Smart Lighting using light sensing LDR sensors:*

An Arduino and a LDR sensor is used to automate the common spaces of a Building. All the lighting of the common space inside a hostel is updated by attaching an arduino coded with a LDR sensor. The LDR sensor detects the lighting ambience and sends a signal of the arduino and the arduino reads the signal and sends information to the bulb or the tubelight to be switched ON when insufficient lighting is available and to be switched off when sufficient lighting is available. This system ensures efficient energy usage, reducing electricity waste while providing seamless automation for hostel residents.

Figure 2(a).

Figure 2(b).

In the above simulation Figure 2(a) and Figure 2(b) an arduino is taken along with a LDR sensor and a LED. The 12th digital pin is taken and then connected to the LED with a 10K Ω resistor, this will serve as the output. The LDR sensor is taken and terminal 1 is connected to the ground and the 2nd terminal is connected to 5V input along a 10k Ω resistor and an A0 analog pin.

In Figure 2(a) the LDR sensor detects the light ambience to be high and thus it sends an analogue signal to the arduino and the LED remains off as the analogue value is too high.

In Figure 2(b) the LDR sensor detects the light ambience to be low and thus it sends an analogue signal to the arduino and the LED glows as the analogue value is within range.

B) Smart Lighting using motion sensing Ultrasonic sensors:

Inside the common hall and the rooms ultrasonic sensors can be used to sense the presence of motion and use that to form a smart light system that is efficient and also saves energy. Unlike traditional light switches that require manual operation, this system helps to automate lighting control by sensing motion. It has a toggle that triggers a signal and an echo which receives that signal after it has reflected back from an object. When a person enters the room, these waves bounce back differently due to movement, allowing the sensor to detect presence and motion.

After the sensor detects the motion it sends a signal to the Arduino that switches the light ON. If no motion is detected the system automatically switches the lights OFF preventing unnecessary energy usage. Ultrasonic sensors can detect both motion and stationary presence ensuring that lights stay ON even when someone is just sitting and not moving.

Figure 3(a).

Figure 3(b).

In the above simulation Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b) an arduino is taken along with a Ultrasonic sensor and a LED. The 3rd digital pin is connected to the trigger pin and the 2nd digital pin is connected to the echo pin of the ultrasonic sensor, the VCC is given 5V supply and the Ground pin is connected to the Ground pin of the arduino. The Led is taken, the anode is connected to the 6th digital pin and the cathode is connected to the ground along with a 10k Ω resistor.

In Figure 3(a) the object is placed within range of the ultrasonic sensor and the sensor is able to detect and send a signal back to the arduino which in return glows the LED.

In Figure 3(b) the object is outside the range of the ultrasonic sensor and the sensor is unable to detect that the arduino does not turn ON the LED.

C) *Integrated System using both LDR and Ultrasonic Sensor :*

While the above methods are used commonly, what if energy could be optimised more efficiently. For that, a more efficient system is used by integrating both the LDR and Ultrasonic sensor. The system helps to predict first the ambience of light around and then it senses human presence and then if both the criteria meets i.e. if the ambience of lighting around is low and human presence was found then and only then the LED glows.

At first the LDR sensor is used to sense the intensity of light around if the intensity is quite high then there is sufficient light around if not then the decision moves to the Ultrasonic sensor. A Ultrasonic sensor is used to detect motion and human presence if found then it automatically turns the LED ON otherwise the LED remains OFF. This system not only optimizes the energy lost during the day due to human negligence but also reduces the unwanted wastage of energy in private spaces when no person is present and lights still glows wasting energy.

Figure 4(a).

Figure 4(b).

Figure 4(c).

Figure 4(d).

In the above simulation Figure 4(a), Figure 4(b), Figure 4(c) and Figure 4(d), an Arduino is connected to a LDR sensor and an Ultrasonic sensor and LED using resistors where needed. The Trig pin of the Ultrasonic Sensor is connected to the 6th digital pin and Echo pin is connected to the 7th pin. The LDR sensor uses

the 5V input for terminal one and the terminal two is connected to the ground along with the A0 pin for sending the sensed reading back to the arduino.

In Figure 4(a) the LDR sensor is used to sense the light intensity as the light intensity is found high the LED does not glow, moreover the object is outside the range of the Ultrasonic sensor.

In Figure 4(b) the LDR sensor is again used to sense the light intensity as the light intensity is found high again similarly the LED does not glow although this time the object is within the range of the Ultrasonic sensor.

In Figure 4(c) the LDR sensor is used to sense the light intensity this time the light intensity is found low next the Ultrasonic Sensor is used to detect the object as the object is found outside the range it again does not glow.

In Figure 4(d) the LDR sensor is used to sense the light intensity here the light intensity is again found low and similarly the Ultrasound sensor is again used to detect the object as this time the object is within the range the LED glows.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The project is integrated with LDR, an ultrasonic sensor to execute the particular domain for sustainable energy savings by developing IoT based automated lighting system. The advantages of an ultrasonic sensor is that it can work in adverse conditions and is not affected by atmospheric changes. It has higher sensing distance (in centimeters and inches) compared to inductive/capacitive proximity sensor types and provides good readings in sensing large sized objects with hard surfaces. The LDR sensor is accessible, affordable, simple to use and understand. These sensors react quickly to variations in light intensity. Its longevity makes it suitable for long term use in devices and systems. These sensors don't consume a lot of electricity making them useful for sustainable development and energy savings. However, Performance these sensors can be affected by changes in temperature, which might result in inconsistent readings in varying weather conditions. The ultrasonic sensor has more difficulties in reading reflections from soft, curved, thin and small objects.

The LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) and Ultrasonic Sensor serve distinct purposes in automated systems. An LDR responds to changes in light intensity, altering its resistance accordingly, with an analogue voltage output and very low power consumption, making it ideal for detecting ambient light conditions. In contrast, an Ultrasonic Sensor operates by emitting ultrasonic waves and measuring the time taken for their return, providing a digital or voltage output. It consists of both an ultrasonic transmitter and receiver and requires moderate power consumption to generate sound waves. While the LDR is suitable for light-based detection, the Ultrasonic Sensor excels in detecting proximity or movement, allowing both to complement each other in energy-efficient systems.

The main purpose of this project was to reduce energy losses mainly due to human negligence. The integrated system provides a way to reduce the energy wasted during unwanted time. If a question may arise how does the suggested system excels from those which are currently present. Although automatic light control using LDR and Ultrasonic sensors are used rather widely, integrating both systems provides a new way of looking into the problem and also optimizing the extra energy losses that was present in the previous systems i.e. with LDR and ultrasonic systems.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This research explores the use of LDR, ultrasonic sensor and Arduino in the domain of energy conservation for sustainable development. It is an effective model which deals with the problems of time delay and solves detection by sensor and solves it. The ultrasonic sensor has been implemented successfully in the model by bridging the previous research gaps. This automated system model can be implemented in personal spaces to common spaces of buildings.

By encouraging energy conservation through automated lighting management and lowering needless power consumption, this project promotes sustainability. It optimizes energy usage in both private and public areas while reducing the need for human interaction. This promotes a beneficial environmental impact by reducing carbon emissions and electricity use ultimately causing a sustainable development. Future studies are recommended to analyze residents' habits using machine learning and adjust lighting accordingly.

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